

Binuclear Transition Metal Complexes of some Novel Schiff Bases derived from Dapsone (An Antileprotic Drug). Part-II. Zinc(II) Complexes

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Binuclear complexes of $Zn_2L_2X_4$ stoichiometry, where L = 4,4'-di(furan/thiophene or pyridine-2-formylimino)diphenylsulphone (abbreviated as FD/TD/PD respectively hereinafter), X = Cl^- , NO_3^- and CH_3COO^- ions, possessing octahedral environment around metal ions, are reported. The complexes have been characterised by elemental analysis, conductivity, magnetic, ir and uv spectral measurements.

Genetic failure of the absorption of zinc in human body results into a poor growth, lesion of the skin and various other mental and physical disorders¹. In allopathic, ayurvedic and homeopathic therapies Zn and its compounds have fairly been recommended for the treatment of skin infections², jaundice, impotency³, eczema and various other skin and psychic disorders⁴. In continuation to our previous communications⁵, we now report the synthesis and characterisation of the complexes of divalent zinc with the Schiff bases derived from the condensation of dapsone with furan/thiophene/pyridine-2-aldehydes.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are stable in air and soluble in DMF, DMSO and THF. Molar conductivity data (Table 1) indicate their non-electrolytic nature. Qualitative tests for anions in aqueous and ethanolic mediums do not give positive results. Elemental analysis and molecular weight data suggest $Zn_2L_2X_4$ stoichiometry for the complexes, where X = Cl^- , NO_3^- and CH_3COO^- ions and L = Schiff bases (FD), (TD) and (PD).

Strong bands at 1 100 and 1 240 cm^{-1} in ligand (FD) are assignable to the furan ring oxygen⁵, 700 and 890 cm^{-1} in ligand (TD) are assignable to the thiophene ring sulphur stretching

vibrations⁶ while in ligand (PD) a sharp band at 1 530 cm^{-1} is assignable to the pyridine ring nitrogen stretching⁷. The ν_{as} and ν_s sulphone vibrations⁸ of dapsone have also been observed at the same frequencies (\sim 1 125, 1 290 cm^{-1} respectively) in all the ligands. Appearance of these bands in the respective ligand molecules indicate that ring oxygen of furan, ring sulphur of thiophene, ring nitrogen of pyridine and the sulphone groups of dapsone have not been effected during the ligand formation reactions. The ν_{as} (NH_2) and ν_s (NH_2) vibrations of dapsone are absent in all the ligands, and a new band appeared at 1 600, 1 610 and \sim 1 600 cm^{-1} respectively, in FD, TD and PD corresponding to the azomethine group⁹, thus confirming the condensation of respective aldehydes with dapsone.

On comparing ir spectra of the complexes with that of the ligands, stretching bands corresponding to the azomethine groups, ring oxygen of furan, thiophene sulphur and pyridine nitrogen in the respective complexes are found invariably shifted (40–60 cm^{-1}) towards negative side indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen¹⁰, ring oxygen of furan¹¹, thiophene sulphur¹² and pyridine nitrogen¹³ with the metal ions in the respective complexes. Red-shifts (\sim 20 cm^{-1}) on complexation, in the out-of-plane and in-plane ring deformation frequencies of thiophenic sulphur and

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Mol. wt.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. cond * $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		N	S	Cl	Zn	
Ligand (FD)	404.4	7.07 (7.93)	7.09 (7.93)	— —	—	2.6
Zn ₂ (FD) ₂ Cl ₄	1081.4	5.22 (5.18)	5.90 (5.93)	13.14 13.11	12.12 (12.09)	7.2
Zn ₂ (FD) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	1187.6	9.46 (9.43)	5.36 (5.40)	— —	10.97 (11.01)	6.2
Zn ₂ (FD) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄	1175.8	4.63 (4.84)	5.69 (5.45)	— —	11.02 (11.13)	6.4
Ligand (TD)	436.5	6.91 (6.42)	21.52 (22.03)	—	—	2.2
Zn ₂ (TD) ₂ Cl ₄	1145.6	4.39 (4.89)	16.81 (16.79)	12.67 12.38	11.20 (11.41)	5.0
Zn ₂ (TD) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	1248.2	9.85 (8.95)	15.39 (15.37)	— —	10.66 (10.44)	5.4
Zn ₂ (TD) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄	1240.0	4.56 (4.52)	15.40 (15.51)	— —	10.54 (10.54)	5.0
Ligand (PD)	426.4	13.02 (13.14)	7.32 (7.52)	—	—	2.8
Zn ₂ (PD) ₂ Cl ₄	1125.5	9.90 (9.96)	5.69 (5.60)	12.26 12.60	11.53 (11.62)	8.0
Zn ₂ (PD) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	1231.7	13.60 (13.60)	5.10 (5.00)	— —	10.00 (10.39)	8.1
Zn ₂ (PD) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄	1219.9	4.78 (4.59)	5.01 (5.26)	— —	10.44 (10.72)	6.0

* In nitrobenzene.

pyridyl nitrogen^{12,14}, in the respective complexes, also indicate the metal-ligand bonding in these complexes through the thiophenic sulphur and pyridyl nitrogen respectively. Observed shifts in these complexes, indicate¹⁵ a considerable transfer of electron density.

Sulphone group stretching bands did not show any appreciable shift on either side, indicating the non-participation of this group in the coordination. However, decrease (20–25%) in the intensity of these bands may be attributed as the effect of strong electronic repulsion imposed by the coordinating uninegative anions on the non-coordinating sulphone group of the ligands. Presence of two coordinating nuclei in the vicinity of sulphone groups (Fig. 1) increases strain on S–O bonds due to high electronic repulsion of the coordinating anions, which results into a change in the electron density at sulphone-oxygen, thus

decreasing the band intensity. In the acetato complexes, comparatively small decrease (~25%) in the intensity of these bands has invariably been noted as reported earlier⁵. It indicates lesser distortion in the symmetry of these complexes as compared to the corresponding chloro and nitrate complexes. It might be due to a weak electronic repulsion exerted by comparatively less electronegative acetate ions on the neighbouring ligands. However, steric factors only can not decide the symmetry of complex molecules and X-rays crystallographic studies may clarify the position more precisely.

Medium intensity absorption bands in the chloro complexes, corresponding to the metal-ligand coordination have been observed in the far-ir region at ~560, 380, ~430, 330 and ~290 cm^{-1} which are assignable to M–O, M–S, M–N (azomethine nitrogen), M–N (pyridyl nitrogen) and M–Cl

TABLE 2—PERTINENT IR STRETCHING VIBRATIONS (cm⁻¹)

Ligand* TD	Zn ₂ (TD) ₂ Cl ₄	Zn ₂ (TD) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	Zn ₂ (TD) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄	Ligand PD	Zn ₂ (PD) ₂ Cl ₄	Zn ₂ (PD) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	Zn ₂ (PD) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄	Assignment
700	660	640	650	—	—	—	—	thiophene ring sulphur stretching
890	850	840	860	—	—	—	—	Pyridine ring nitrogen stretching
—	—	—	—	1 530	1 480	1 500	1 470	—
1120	1 120	1 122	1 118	1 122	1 125	~ 1 122	~ 1 120	v _{as} sulphonic group
1290	~ 1 290	1 292	1 290	1 295	~ 1 290	1 292	~ 1 290	v _s sulphonic group
1610	1 550	1 560	1 570	~ 1 600	1565	1 550	1 570	ν _{C=N} azomethine group
—	445	450	430	—	400	390	410	ν _{M-N} (azomethine) nitrogen
—	—	—	—	—	330	315	320	ν _{M-N} (pyridine) nitrogen
—	380	380	390	—	—	—	—	ν _{M-S} (thiophenic) sulphur
—	310	—	—	—	275	—	—	ν _{M-Cl}
—	—	470	—	—	—	460	—	ν _{M-NO₃}
—	—	—	1 315, 1 630	—	—	—	-1 310, 1 630	v _{as} , v _s carboxylic
—	—	—	500	—	—	—	570	ν _{M-O} carboxylic oxygen
Ligand FD	Zn ₂ (FD) ₂ Cl ₄	Zn ₂ (FD) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	Zn ₂ (FD) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄					Assignment
1 100	1 065	1 080	—	—	—	—	1 060	furan ring oxygen stretching
~ 1 240	1 190	1 200	—	—	—	—	1 180	v _{as} sulphonic group
~ 1 125	1 120	~ 1 122	—	1 120	—	—	—	v _s sulphonic group
1 290	~ 1 292	1 288	—	1 290	—	—	—	ν _{C=N} azomethine group
1 600	1 560	1 540	—	1 555	—	—	—	ν _{M-Cl}
—	310	—	—	—	—	—	—	ν _{M-NO₃}
—	—	380	—	—	—	—	—	v _{as} , v _s carboxylic
—	—	—	1 310, 1 620	—	—	—	—	ν _{M-O} carboxylic oxygen
—	—	—	500	—	—	—	—	ν _{M-O} furan oxygen
—	555	560	560	—	—	—	—	—

*TD=4,4'-di(thiophene-2-formylimino)diphenyl sulphone; PD=4,4'-di(pyridine-2-formylimino)diphenyl sulphone, FD = 4,4-di(furan-2-formylimino)diphenyl sulphone.

stretching vibrations respectively^{15,17}. In the nitrate complexes, three additional sharp bands observed at 1 000, 1 250 and 1 410 cm⁻¹ are assignable to v₂, v₁ and v₄ modes of coordinating nitrate ion. Since the magnitude of separation between v₄ and v₁ bands is 160 cm⁻¹, therefore coordination of nitrate ions in a unidentate manner is confirmed¹⁸. Medium intensity bands around 460 and 380 cm⁻¹ in these complexes, are assignable to M-N (azomethine) and M-N (nitrate) stretching vibrations¹⁹. The v_{as} and v_s carboxylic modes of acetate ions assignable at 1 400 and 1 560 cm⁻¹ respectively²⁰, have been found to be shifted to ~ 1 310 and 1 630 cm⁻¹ respectively. This larger separation between the v_{as} and v_s frequencies, thus, confirms the coordination of acetate as a unidentate anion through the C-O⁻ moiety of the carboxylic group²¹. Metal-ligand bonding

vibrations in these complexes, have also been observed in the expected range.

All the complexes are found to be diamagnetic in character. Broad bands observed around 28 000–28 500 cm⁻¹ in their electronic spectra, presumably, correspond to the charge transfer transitions only. The complexes are suggested as binuclear octahedral on the basis of solubility tests, low conductance, high m.p., spectral, elemental analysis and molecular weight data.

Experimental

Dapsone (Sigma), thiophene-2-aldehyde (Aldrich) and pyridine-2-aldehyde (Aldrich) were used as such. Furan-2-aldehyde and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Elemental analysis and all physicochemical measurements were done

X = Cl^- , NO_3^- and CH_3COO^- ; A = O/S/N of the ligand
Fig. 1

as reported earlier⁵. The respective aldehydes (0.1 mol) were mixed separately with dapsone (0.05 mol) in absolute ethanol (150 ml). The mixtures were refluxed for 8 h using CaCl_2 guard tube. Then ethanol (95–100 ml) was distilled off from each mixture and the residual solutions were cooled in freezing mixture for 4 h. Crystalline Schiff bases were filtered, recrystallised from absolute ethanol and dried at 84–85°, yield 68–70% with respect to dapsone [m.p. 168° (FD), 192° (TD) and 158° (PD)]. Saturated ethanolic solutions of respective ligands (0.005 mol) and the respective metal salts (0.02 mol) were mixed together and refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixtures were cooled in ice for 2 h. Crystalline complexes that separated out were washed with ice-cold ethanol and dried at 84–85°, yields 60–62%.

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